

Walking the Talk: *Is-Ought* as Transdisciplinarity and as a Trans-Domain Approach for Researchers, Teachers, and Students

Jean-Luc Patry

Introduction

Since its very beginning, philosophy has been a system of statements, has been talking. Some philosophers have not only talked about the world and in particular about how it should be, but have also acted accordingly, i.e., they walked the talk. Among those who have done so, one can mention Socrates, who even created a method of dialogue that was named after him, but also lived up to his philosophy and went so far as to die in fulfillment of the principles he had established. Others were very active politicians in the first place, but had a strong philosophical background, like Mahatma Gandhi, Martin Luther King, and Nelson Mandela; they, too, walked their talk. However, while we can find prototypical people who did so, walking the talk itself has not been analyzed very often, and in particular, teaching people to walk the talk has rarely been addressed.

A central topic in both talking and walking is the so-called *Is-Ought* problem, i.e., the distinction between the two domains¹ *Is* and *Ought* and (possible) relations between them. In philosophy, this distinction was first addressed by David Hume (1739, pp. 244f.), and it has been an important topic in philosophy since. However, this debate has had little resonance for the walk side, or as Daston (2014, p. 579) said, among the “avant-garde and the rearguard, the devout and the secular, the learned elite and the lay public scientists,” in particular with respect to social issues, such as “deducing” practical recommendations from empirical research results (Friedrich, 2005; 2010). As regards the walk, however, both *Is* and *Ought* are of central importance, as people, in their practical decision-making regarding actions, need to consider both the actual conditions of the situation (the *Is*) and the goals they want to achieve (Patry, 1991b), which they are supposed to justify (the *Ought*). This holds in education, where the educators seek to achieve goals which they are asked to justify explicitly (Klafki, 1984), but in everyday situations as well, since people always want to achieve goals, even if they often do not think about justifying them.

In the present paper, the aim is to show how philosophical talk can have an impact on practice (the walk) in education and through education on students’ practical decision-making in (fictional) situations presenting dilemmas. In the second section, the *Is-Ought* problem is roughly sketched out from the philosophical perspective. Since *Is* and *Ought* are considered to be different disciplines, the “relationship” can be seen as an issue of transdisciplinarity, as discussed in the third section, resulting in the proposition to replace transdisciplinarity with Trans-Domain Approaches (TDAs), with a focus on TDA as a system of statements (talk). In the fourth section, the latter is distinguished from the practice-oriented TDA (walk), and the relations are discussed.

¹ The term *domain* and how it is used in this paper will be explained below. These two domains will systematically be presented in italics and capitalized.

In the fifth section, a practical approach—Values *and* Knowledge Education (VaKE)—is briefly introduced and analyzed with respect to *Is* and *Ought*, using the two TDA frameworks (TDA as theory and practice-oriented TDA). In the conclusions, the importance of the concept of TDA and its use for the *Is-Ought* problem on the talk and on the walk levels are discussed, and it is shown how VaKE can be a valuable tool for dealing appropriately with the *Is-Ought* problem and how to educate people to apply it.

1. *Talk: The Is-Ought Problem*

The *Is-Ought* problem as addressed in this paper deals only with types of statements, not with the many interpretations of the *Is-Ought* problem in history (see, for instance, Curry, 2006). The claim is that *Is*-statements and *Ought*-statements are different and that it is not possible to establish logical links between them. For this discussion, the following types of statements are distinguished:

- Descriptive statements (belonging to the domain *Is*) are statements of the type “x is (was, will be) the case.” They refer to (presumed) facts and can be tested, at least in principle, through observation of any kind. *In principle* means here that the following issues are acknowledged: (1) Observations depend on our perceptual apparatus with all its limits and biases; (2) observation of any kind is subject to random and systematic errors (which is a complex issue that I cannot deal with here—I did elsewhere with respect to many issues related with situation specificity [Patry, 2011]); (3) statements are considered as descriptive even if the described phenomenon (supposedly) does not exist (e.g., “Unicorns are white.”); (4) the described characteristics of a phenomenon can be inferred instead of directly observed; etc. Scientific descriptive theories have been tested empirically. For practical actions, people use subjective descriptive theories. Using a correspondence theory of truth, descriptive statements (whether scientific or subjective) can be true or wrong; in a constructivist perspective (Patry, 2016), they are statements expressing what the author believes to be (or not to be) fact or reality; these subjective theories usually have been shown to be useful and successful in achieving goals in practical situations.
- Normative or prescriptive statements (belonging to the domain *Ought*) are statements of the type “x ought to be the case.” or “x ought to be done.” They refer to requirements, to what must be done or what is normatively necessary. This is independent of whether one thinks this ought to be done or be the case. Evaluative statements belong also to the domain *Ought*; these are statements that ascribe a value (like “good,” “beautiful,” etc.) to a state of affairs (fact or action, etc.). These statements are descriptive insofar as they describe some characteristics of a state of affairs, and normative or prescriptive insofar as they express that the state of affairs is normatively or not normatively required (ought or ought not to be). In agreement with Schurz (e.g., 2004), such statements are considered as normative as well. How such statements can be justified is part of the *Is-Ought* problem, namely regarding whether they can be justified through facts.
- Mixed statements are statements that contain descriptive as well as normative components.

Hume (1739, pp. 244f.) was the first to pronounce the thesis that a strict separation exists between *Is* and *Ought*. In a simplified version, it states that one type cannot be justified by (reduced to, deduced from, or even logically related to, etc.) the other one (Schurz, 1995). The logical support for Hume's thesis is very complex (see Schurz, 1995, 1997, 2004, 2010, 2020; Morscher, 2018, 2021; etc.) and cannot be discussed here.

Normative statements are different from statements of the type “person y thinks that x ought to be the case,” as the statement is clearly descriptive; it can be checked, e.g., through asking this person what he or she thinks. According to Hume's thesis, the second part of the statement cannot be tested through observation of any kind. Rather, such statements need to be argued for through ethical justification.

Schurz (2010, p. 202) concretized Hume's thesis: “No purely normative conclusion which is not already logically true is inferable from a consistent set of purely descriptive premises.” However, many statements that are claimed to be purely descriptive contain in fact hidden normative components (Schurz, 1995, p. 163), either because the latter are considered as trivial or because nonrational processes are involved (e.g., Rogerson et al., 2011). It is a matter of scientific and argumentative honesty and transparency to identify and separate the descriptive and the normative components of such statements (Schurz, 2004, p. 15). This way, normative statements cannot be tacitly insinuated, whether intentionally or not; instead, arguments in favor of the normative statements can be put forward. For sake of transparency, such argumentative support is required, even if it consists simply in ascertaining that the normative component is trivial. Therefore, Hume's thesis is not only logically supported, but also an ethical requirement: We must avoid hidden values. This holds for science, where normative statements must be laid open so that they can be communicated and possibly criticized—such a procedure satisfies two important criteria of science: (1) that statements must be communicated, and (2) that they can be criticized within the scientific community. This holds also for everyday behavior, because people are often not aware of the values underlying their decisions (regarding sensitivity for values issues in given situations, see Reynolds & Miller, 2015; Hamlin & Tan, 2020); if they were to think about these values and their justification, they might decide differently.

One can conceive of mixed statements that establish a relation between descriptive and normative statements: so-called bridge principles. Some of them are sometimes claimed to be almost self-evident because they are plausible according to most ethical theories (“*fast analytisch wahr*,” Schurz, 2004, pp. 23f.). The first is “What is required [*Ought*-component] must be feasible at least to some degree [*Is*-component: feasibility]” (Kant, 1956, A548/B576, p. 534)—in the short version, “Ought implies Can”; in other words, One is not allowed to ask someone to do something that he or she is not able to do. The second example is “Necessary consequences of or necessary means for [*Is*-component] required [*Ought* component] actions or states of affairs are also required.” In other words, one can only require something where the conditions or consequences are also approved. Although these bridge principles are “almost self-evident,” it is imperative to make them explicit if applied; the reasons for that are the same as those for goals and their justification, as discussed above. And in situations when a person has to give priority to one value or norm over the other—in moral dilemmas, for example—both bridge principles become problematic.

A moral dilemma consists of a decision situation in which the protagonist has to decide between two behavioral options which are incompatible, i.e., cannot be performed simultaneously; acting according to the first option will comply with a set of norms or values, but break another set of norms which is achieved through the second behavioral option—the latter, however, will break the norms that the first option fulfills. In such difficult situations, the respective values are contested, as the protagonist has to give priority to one set (related to one behavior option) to the detriment of the ones linked to the other option. In such dilemmas, “*Ought* implies *Can*” becomes problematic, as *Can* is impossible for the two options simultaneously, and hence if this bridge principle is applied, it is inappropriate to require both *Oughts* simultaneously, since this requirement cannot be fulfilled (Williams, 1973)—this is the bridge principle “*Ought* implies *Can*” on a meta-level, where the *Can* is impossible on logical grounds (since one cannot achieve two actions simultaneously that mutually exclude each other).

Ethical questions become relevant primarily in (moral) dilemmas. In such situations of contested values or norms, it is a necessity to discuss them. If there is agreement about the values or the protagonist does not recognize competing values (possibly because of lack of moral sensitivity), there is no need to worry about them. One must mention, however, that life is full of antinomies, i.e., opposing requirements or demands of the situation, or in other words, we are very often confronted with multiple goals that cannot be achieved simultaneously (Patry, 1991b, 2012)—however, we often recognize such conflicts only if we are asked to make our goals explicit (Patry, 2005).

The application of Hume’s thesis does not mean that scientists must avoid using values in their statements, like those that for instance Brezinka (1994) requires for educational research (“*Erziehungswissenschaft*”); indeed, a differentiated analysis shows that in empirical educational research, normative statements cannot be avoided. Science cannot be values-free (Kincaid et al., 2007); educational research, in particular, cannot restrain from values judgments since education itself always involves values goals, etc. (Patry, 2006), which need to be justified; further, the choice of the research topic is always based on (personal or societal) values, and the research process must follow research ethics (J.-L. Patry & P. Patry, 2003); and finally, often, authors of reports derive practical recommendations from their research results, which again are normative (Patry, 2006). It is inevitable, thus, that one addresses both *Is* and *Ought* in educational research, and this must be made explicit to satisfy the scientific criterion of transparency.

However, the support of the two types of statements follows different argumentation patterns (Zecha, 1984). Descriptive statements refer directly or at least indirectly to observation of some kind—with all the ensuing problems of descriptive research (once the normative issues of this research are dealt with appropriately). In contrast, normative statements can only be justified through referring to superordinate values, i.e., values that encompass, but are not identical with, subordinate value; for instance, the value *human dignity* is superordinate to the value *esteeming interaction*. Besides esteem, there are other issues pertaining to dignity, such as accepting that other people have different opinion, etc. (see the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, United Nations, 1948, where the general principle of dignity is addressed as a key issue of the preamble on which all the subsequent articles are based). This leads to the so-called Münchhausen trilemma (see Albert, 1985, pp. 18f.): the justification of a value v_1 through a superordinary value v_2 requires that v_2 also be justified, which is only possible through a value v_3 that is superordinary to v_2 , and

so on. The trilemma consists in three possibilities, each of which is unacceptable or not satisfactory. Albert called this situation “Münchhausen” in reference to the famous lying Baron who pretended to have pulled himself and his horse out of a swamp by his own hair. The three possibilities are

1. an *infinite regress*, which seems to arise from the necessity to go further and further back in the search for foundations, and which, since it is in practice impossible, affords no secure basis;
2. a *logical circle* in the deduction, which arises because, in the process of justification, statements are used which were characterized before as need in foundation, so that they can provide no secure basis; and, finally,
3. the *breaking-off of the process* at a particular point, which, admittedly, can always be done in principle, but involves an arbitrary suspension of the principle of sufficient justification. (Albert, 1985, p. 18)

Infinite regress is not feasible, and the circular argument (the Münchhausen solution) is unacceptable; hence only the third option can be considered. This means that one must decide on a “highest value” which is not scrutinized. For educational purposes, intuitively, the value “Human Dignity” is chosen, with reference to the United Nations’ (1948) Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

Although *Is* and *Ought* belong to different domains and cannot logically be related with each other, from a different perspective, and referring to practical decision-making, *Is* and *Ought* need to be considered simultaneously. The principle is: Values without knowledge is blind; knowledge without societal values leads to selfishness and is a threat to humankind. This means that just defending certain values (*Ought* values), even the most justified ones, will not help to change the world if there is no knowledge (*Is*) about the reasons for the respective problems and about possibilities to change them. On the other hand, someone who may have knowledge about such issues but does not prioritize the value of better conditions for mankind and the universe over his or her personal wellbeing will not be motivated to do anything about the problem at stake: quite the opposite. As Francis Bacon (1597, qtd.in Baggaley et al., 2013, p. 898) said, “*knowledge is power,*” and power is likely to be abused if not controlled by societal values.

Take as example one of the Great Challenges to humankind and the planet: the climate crisis. To address this challenge, one needs, on one hand, knowledge about the fact that there is global warming, what this means, and the reasons it is occurring (*Is*); but one also needs the motivation to do something about it, which means reducing one’s comfort in favor of the greater good. This is a values preference (personal comfort vs. greater good) which can only be decided on ethical grounds (*Ought*). Commitment for the greater good without knowledge about facts (in particular what can be done, e.g., how to reduce CO₂, and arguments against intervening, e.g., the economic consequences of doing so), i.e., *Ought* without *Is*, leads to blind activism and fundamentalism and will have little impact on the climate. In contrast, knowledge of issues concerning global warming without prioritizing the greater good (*Is* without *Ought*) increases the climate problem because the person will not do anything to fight it or even deny that there is a climate change; our perception is dependent on our values! More generally, for all Great Challenges (discrimination, global warming, corruption, lies, pandemics, racism, sexism, violence, to name just a few) and for most personal decisions, considering both *Is* and *Ought* is required.

The concept “Values without knowledge is blind; knowledge without societal values is dangerous” has been stated thus by Hume: “Human nature being compos’d of two principal parts, which are requisite in all its actions, the affections and understanding; ‘tis certain, that the blind motions of the former, without the direction of the latter, incapacitate men for society” (1739, p. 256). For science, it follows that *Is* and *Ought* need to be related to each other. For education, this leads to the requirement that one should educate for both knowledge (education in the domain of *Is*: acquiring knowledge of viable descriptive statements) and values (education in the domain of *Ought*: acquiring viable values systems), and also that these two domains are to be related to each other; knowledge and values must address the same topic (e.g., a Great Challenge) and cannot be seen as independent.

2. *Transdisciplinarity, Domains, and Trans-Domain Approaches (TDAs) as Systems of Statements*

Is and *Ought* refer to different scientific disciplines; establishing a relationship between them, hence, is an issue of transdisciplinarity. *Is* is dealt with in different descriptive scientific disciplines like science, technology, psychology, sociology, etc. In contrast, *Ought* is the topic of philosophy, more precisely of ethics (and meta-ethics). Establishing a relationship between *Is* and *Ought*, as required at the end of the last section, hence, means that these disciplines cannot be seen independently, but must be addressed simultaneously under a common framework. This is dealt with in the literature under the title of transdisciplinarity (see also Scholz & Steiner, 2015, p. 528; Bauer & Meyerhuber, 2020; and many others). Transdisciplinarity can be defined as consisting of a “shared conceptual framework drawing together disciplinary-specific theories, concepts, and approaches to address (a) common problem” (Rosenfield, 1992, table 3). Referring to transdisciplinarity permits us to connect the *Is-Ought* problem addressed in the previous section with the discussions that have been underway since Jantsch (1947) first introduced the term (see also OECD/CERI, 1972, which will also be capitalized on in the following discussion (see also Patry, 2022a, 2022b).

However, the word *disciplines* opens up a sociological category (Patry, 2022a) in several regards:

- Disciplines are intellectual and social structures;
- they diffuse types of social organizations for the production of particular knowledge (Weingart & Stehr, 2000, p. xiv);
- they define themselves and can be defined in several ways (Van Assche, 2013);
- they serve to defend territories within the scientific community (Weingart, 2000, p. 28);
- they have institutional consequences (Mittelstrass, 2018);
- they are biased, among others by a Western (and often Eurocentric) concept of a valid approach to knowledge (Judge, 1991);
- they underwent important changes in history, as some disciplines disappeared, and most of the remaining ones underwent increasing specialization (Bromme & Kienhues, 2014, p. 56);
- they refer to the historically grown organization of science and not to a stable category (Balsiger, 2005, pp. 51-57; Mittelstrass, 2018, p. S71);

- today's disciplines are so heterogeneous and defined so differently that it is impossible to find common denominators and boundaries (Van Assche, 2013);
- disciplines are interrelated in different ways, and the science system is considered "as non-linear, but turning on itself in an endless spiral, to say nothing of the numerous inter-connections among the terms" (Piaget, 1972, p. 131);
- they refer to social structures to be addressed in the sociology of science (Van Assche, 2013).

This means that disciplines are used to organize science according to criteria which are not epistemological but historical, sociological, organizational, etc.; hence, the concept of disciplines is inappropriate for the purpose of finding a common underlying theoretical framework (such as combining *Is* and *Ought*), which is an epistemological endeavor.

Instead of *disciplines*, it is proposed to use the concept of *domain*. In the present context, this term does not refer to the structure of internet addresses according to the Domain Name System (DNS). Rather, the root is in the domains of knowledge, i.e., the "semantic knowledge for a particular field" (Newberry et al., 2021, p. 660). A domain consists of the knowledge of specialists in a specific, delimited field, including, but not restricted to, a specialized discipline. It is, hence, a relatively closed system of statements, a set of research topics or thematic fields that is addressed with a homogeneous system of related theories that are studied with similar methods; such a system is clearly distinct from other such systems, with the delimitations being scientifically grounded. These theories will be called Domain-specific Theories (DT). The definition of domains is kept open to permit its application in different contexts. In particular, the focus will not be on the domains themselves, but on the lack of obvious relations *between* two or more domains. The goal of TDA research is the same as the one for transdisciplinarity: to provide as much insight as possible about a research topic, notwithstanding the boundaries that may exist or have been erected between different fields of research. However, the concept of domains is wider and more flexible than the one of disciplines, and can be argued about more precisely since the relationships or lack thereof are scientific and do not depend on the haphazardness of the distinction between disciplines.

Instead of transdisciplinarity, consequently, the concept of Trans-Domain Approaches (TDA) will be used. A TDA is defined as *a system of scientific statements that relates to the theories of different domains and adds new issues to the ones already contained in the respective domain-specific theories in order to achieve a goal that cannot be reached within one domain* (Patry, 2022a, p. 3). The different aspects of this definition are addressed in a theory of TDA.

This theory of TDA is proposed as follows (for details, see Patry, 2022a, 2022b; Patry et al., 2022; Patry & Weyringer, 2019). First, one can distinguish a TDA as system of statements (or theories) and as actions:

A TDA consists of a scientific system of theories that includes a [General Theory] GT that connects, integrates, and transcends a set of specialized (domain-specific) theories (DTs), but does not replace them. This goes beyond a simple combination of the domains (which would be called interdisciplinarity or inter-domain approach); rather, the GT contains more information than can be found in the combined theories of the respective domains or DTs alone, but does not include all information contained in the

respective DTs. The GT, hence, is a superordinate theory.... The DTs, in turn, address some issues of the research topic with more details but narrower bandwidth than the GT as they focus only on certain issues and do not consider other ones that, from the perspective of TDA, would be important as well. (Patry, 2022a, p. 3)

A superordinate theory is a theory that addresses issues that are already the topic of two or more other theories (subordinate theories) and that relates them with each other; for instance, the Cognitive-Affective Personality System (CAPS; Mischel & Shoda, 1995) is superordinate to six subordinate theories that the authors call Cognitive-Affective Units (CAUS): competence, perception, expectancies, values and goals, self-regulatory plans, and emotions. Each of these, in turn, is superordinate to a set of subordinate theories (the theory of competences, for instance, includes theories dealing with different types of intelligence, creativity, subjective theories, etc.), which again are superordinate to sets of subordinate theories on a lower level (for intelligence, for instance, the different types of intelligence according to the theory of multiple intelligence; Gardner, 1993). Some have called such superordinate theories “meta-theories” (e.g., Shoda & Mischel, 2006 with respect to the CAPS), but this is inappropriate, since meta-theories are theories *about* theories, whereas superordinate theories are theories that *include* other theories (for details, see Patry, 2014). In the case of meta-theories, the object is theories, which have as object phenomena or norms, while in the latter case, the object can be the same for superordinate and subordinate theories, namely phenomena and/or norms.

The TDA is represented graphically in figure 1, showing the distinction of the General Theory (GT) from the Domain-Specific Theories (DT), with the former being superordinate to the latter (this figure was inspired by Rousseau et al., 2018, p. 53). Applying this principle to the *Is-Ought* problem results in the hierarchy presented figure 2, with two levels: the superordinate level addresses the General Theory about education, since the aim of the present paper is to show how philosophical talk about *Is* and *Ought* can have an impact on practice (the walk) through education. The Specific Theories are *Is* (DT 1) and *Ought* (DT 2). On the subordinate level, new TDAs can be established (TDA' 1, TDA' 2); the prime symbol should signal that the TDAs are on a subordinate level. The respective Domain-Specific Theories DT 1 and DT 2 become General Theories GT' 1 and GT' 2, respectively, for the subordinate Domain-Specific Theories DT' 1.1 etc. For instance, a descriptive framework about education (G' 1) could present the distinction between instruction (telling people what they are supposed to know; DT' 1.1), construction (letting people find out for themselves the content, following the principles of constructivism, e.g., von Glasersfeld, 1995; DT' 1.2), and other educational principles; a distinction in the *Ought* domain could be between deontic concepts (I should do x because the principle underlying x must be applied; DT' 2.1) and teleological concepts (I should do x because the consequences of doing x must be achieved; DT' 2.2). This hierarchy can be extended, with the DT's becoming GT's on the subordinate level double-prime (this is not represented in fig. 2). One can imagine different concepts of differentiation; for instance, one can conceive an alternative TDA' 2*, where content-oriented domains, like justice (DT' 2.1*), care (DT' 2.2*), truthfulness (DT' 2.3*), etc., are distinguished—the asterisk should signal that this is another possibility on the same level. Which alternative to choose will depend on the topic of research or on the problem addressed, or on the preferences of the researcher.

Figure 1: TDA as relationships between General Theory (GT), Domain-specific Theories (DTs), domains, and a research topic (from Patry, 2022a, p. 4)

Super-ordinate level (TDA)	General Theory (GT) Theory about Education					
	Domain-Specific Theory DT 1 <i>Is</i>			Domain-Specific Theory DT 2 <i>Ought</i>		
Sub-ordinate level (TDA's)	GT' 1 = DT 1 <i>Is</i>			GT' 2 = DT 2 <i>Ought</i>		
	DT' 1.1 Instruction	DT' 1.2 Construc- tion	DT' 1.3 ...	DT' 2.1 Deontic concepts	DT' 2.2 Teleological concepts	

Figure 2: TDA for *Is-Ought* in education: a hierarchy

3. Practice-oriented TDAs

The theory-practice transfer—or, in the terminology used here, the move from the talk to the walk—is hampered by many problems (Patry, 2018). Among them, the generality-concreteness antinomy is particularly important (Patry, 2017). This antinomy states that the more general a statement is, the less concrete it can be (based on Herrmann, 1979a, pp. 160ff.; 1979b, pp. 232). This holds in particular for social interactions because they are situation specific, and it also applies to descriptive (Patry, 1991a) as well as normative statements (Elliott, 2015). The talks in science and philosophy, e.g., the TDA about *Is* and *Ought* (figure 2, superordinate level), are usually very general: the claim in most studies is that the statements apply for all possible situations, people, times, etc.: only a few studies express explicit restrictions with respect to the bandwidth of the validity of the statements. Further, when referring to research studies from the literature, researchers almost never consider that the statements they cite might not apply to the situation studied in their own research. However, this claim is not justified for many reasons (see Patry,

2019, for some of these reasons), and the application might be erroneous. Only the theories that have been tested might have a certain validity across different situations and conditions, but if so, only on a very abstract level, so that the specific conditions (e.g., the concrete situation) in which people must decide what to do cannot be taken into account.

Practical decision-making (walk) requires concreteness. When I have to decide what to do in a specific situation, I must take into consideration all specificities that may be important in this situation; a slight change in one of the characteristics may lead to a completely different decision. For example, how I decide to act in a conflict situation will depend on the type of conflict, on its history, on the type of relationship to it, on the goals I want to achieve and the respective importance of goals that can be antinomic, on other people involved, etc. All these issues cannot be taken into account at the talk level (e.g., in philosophical theories). The move from talk to walk, then, is the transfer of abstract, general statements to concrete decisions to be taken while considering all the relevant details of the given specific situation.

This problem cannot be solved within a TDA as a system of statements because statements will always be general and abstract (an exception might be found in action research in the sense of Elliott, 1978, but its results are then highly limited in the generalizability scope), and actions need a specific and concrete decision base. Instead, a *TDA as action* is required. For this, the model of theory-practice transfer developed by Patry (2022a, p. 5, based on Patry, 1989) can be used (an adapted version with particular consideration of *Is* and *Ought* is presented in fig. 3).

Figure 3: Model of the theory-practice transfer, focusing in particular on *Is* and *Ought* (based on Patry, 2022a, p. 5)

According to this model (which can be considered as a superordinate theory with a series of subordinate theories), one can distinguish three roles: those of researcher, mediator, and practitioner¹:

- The *researchers* produce and test theories. For this, they need to refer to both the *Ought* and the *Is* domains: they decide on the research topic, which depends on, among other things, their values (*Ought*), and capitalize on the work of previous researchers, which is described in the literature or through other communication channels (*Is*); they develop and test theories, which may include descriptive (*Is*) and normative (*Ought*) theories; from the results, they draw conclusions, in particular with respect to practice, which depends on normative premises (e.g., what goal do I want to achieve, and why?).
- The *mediators* process scientific theories so that practitioners can grab their central messages and use them in their decision-making; examples are textbooks or teacher education courses. For this, the mediators use scientific theories (which can be found in the literature—descriptive), of which they select those that they think to be important for the practitioners—this is a decision based on normative premises along with other criteria. Further, they present the selected theories in a form they judge to be appropriate for the practitioner, which also depends on normative premises (e.g., when emphasizing certain issues and neglecting others, or when providing concrete examples chosen for good—normative—reasons) along with other things.
- The practitioners, first, integrate the communicated information from the mediators into their system of subjective theories, i.e., their system of beliefs and convictions—both descriptive and normative—about the world and themselves (Groeben et al., 1988); Piaget (1985) calls this assimilation and accommodation. However, the practitioners do not integrate the information as presented; rather, they select what seems important to them, and they add interpretations (e.g., prototypical examples from their own experience) that are not included in the mediator’s message. Such selections and additional interpretations depend on the practitioner’s normative concepts, among other things.
- Based on their system of subjective theories—which contains not only scientific insight but also many concepts they may never have thought about, as well as further goals and other norms—and on their perception and interpretation of the given situation, the practitioners decide what they want to do in this situation. Which elements of their system of subjective theories they select for decision-making, how they transfer them into an action decision, and how they implement the decision will depend on, among other things, normative premises, most importantly on the goals they want to achieve. (These goals and possibly their justification are parts of the system of subjective theories).

As can be seen in the above, all of the roles involve both descriptive (*Is*) and normative (*Ought*) components and combine them in some way (how this is done is a complex topic which cannot be dealt with here; see Gastager & Patry, 2018, for some considerations in this regard). The respective

¹ It is possible that the same person performs two or even three roles successively, such as a teacher (practitioner) who acts also as researcher, or a researcher who writes textbooks for practitioners (mediator), or even a teacher who does research and does teacher-training.

person (researcher, mediator, practitioner) takes some decision based on both descriptive and normative premises. In the terminology used above, those premises are the *talk* (even the subjective theories must be considered talk, as they consist of, or can be reconstructed as, systems of statements), always capitalizing on several domain-specific theories from the domains *Is* and *Ought* and the respective subordinate domain-specific theories, thus based on the respective TDAs. In any case, this TDA will distinguish the domains *Is* and *Ought*, as in figure 2 (superordinate level). One can analyze the possibilities on the subordinate level to identify the three roles. This is rarely done for the researcher; one can interpret Mahoney (1976) and Faust (1984) for the *Is* domain (GT' 1 in fig. 2) and Patry & Patry (2003) for the *Ought* domain (GT' 2) as such TDA's, although they are not discussed in that way and with that terminology. As to the role of mediator, discussion has mainly been on teacher trainers; an example is the analysis of the mentors' subjective theories when discussing the lesson of a pre-service teacher in internship (Roither, 2014), where *Is* as well as *Ought* is addressed. For the practitioners, several analyses have been done, in particular those discussed in Gastager & Patry (2018). While the respective TDAs and TDA's of the researchers were discussed on a general (and therefore abstract) level, the discussions of the other two roles of TDAs and TDA's, addressed in Roither and in Gastager & Patry, referred to specific situations to permit the discussions to be very concrete. However, one must mention that addressing situation-specific issues in practice, as would be necessary for such an endeavor, is rather rare in educational research.

In all the decisions of the researchers, mediators, and practitioners, the theoretical framework available (descriptive and normative: talk) is general and abstract (although to a different degree), whereas the decision itself as preparation to the walk requires a specific and concrete base. The generality-concreteness antinomy with which the practitioner is confronted here leaves a vacancy between the respective talks and the concrete situation-specific base for the walk. To fill this vacancy, the decider has to be creative and formulate his or her own ideas and transfer concepts. This creative act has been called *pedagogical tact* by Herbart (1802/1896), and is discussed in detail by, among others, Burghardt et al. (2015), Burghardt & Zirfas (2019), and Gastager & Patry (2018). One can see that the TDA as action is an achievement of the respective actors; it rests on TDAs as systems of statements, but clearly goes beyond them.

4. *Walk: Values and Knowledge Education (VaKE)*

So far, the movement from talk to walk has been discussed with respect to the practitioners. In the present section, I will go a step further and address the question of teaching students to achieve this transfer, taking into account *Is* and *Ought*. The teaching-learning method to be presented is called Values and Knowledge Education (VaKE; Weyringer et al., 2022). It is a constructivist approach that combines values education (educating for *Ought*) and knowledge education (acquiring knowledge about *Is*) with mutual reference. The starting point of the process is a moral dilemma. As said above, such a dilemma consists of a situation in which a protagonist has to decide which of two alternatives to undertake. Whatever he or she does, he or she will violate some value. For instance, the protagonist has to decide whether to support or to oppose the building of a freeway around a small town. If he or she supports this to comply with values like keeping traffic out of the city center, seeking economic advantages, etc., he or she will break values like reducing traffic and instead increase the emission of harmful substances, avoid the sealing of the soil surface, etc. The two groups of values cannot be achieved simultaneously. And as

mentioned above, it is in the discussion of such dilemmas that moral issues become relevant; hence, they are at the core of practical ethics.

In such a moral dilemma, the students are highly motivated to discuss the justification of their normative preferences. Research has shown that such discussions foster competence in arguing in favor of or against values (e.g., Lind, 2016). A framework to analyze this can be based on Kohlberg's (1984) stage theory of moral judgment competence, which goes from egoism (stage 1) to principle-guided morality (stage 6). However, the theoretical framework of *VaKE* is not Kohlbergian in the sense of Kohlberg (1981, 1984), not even neo-Kohlbergian (e.g., Rest et al., 2000; Thoma, 2014); rather, it can be called *post-Kohlbergian* (see also Arnold, 2000; Lapsley & Narvaez, 2005). In agreement with the Kohlbergian or neo-Kohlbergian approaches, some key issues are kept, such as the constructivist background with assimilation, disequilibrium and accommodation as *modus operandi* of development, autonomy and universality as overarching values—i.e., the approach is *prescriptivist* and not ethically relativistic (Kohlberg, 1971), and the focus is on *reasoning* and on the *justification* of values instead of on values indoctrination. In contrast, *VaKE* differs from the (neo-) Kohlbergian concepts in the following regards, dealing with *Is* and *Ought* (other differences are not discussed here; see Patry et al., in prep.):

- By its very concept, in *VaKE*, the values education framework (education of *Ought*) is *combined with theories of knowledge acquisition* (acquisition of *Is*)—in the sense of the TDA on the superordinate level, see figure 2—and with other theories.
- It refers not only to moral principles underlying one's actions (*deontic* perspective; see DT' 2.1 in fig. 2), but also to the consequences of one's action (*teleological* concepts; see DT' 2.2).
- It refers not only to moral, but also to *other values* (e.g., personal interest, such as caring for one's own safety and health).

In *VaKE*, the moral dilemma is discussed by the participants, with the focus on the justification of the chosen values preferences. However, the dilemma is conceived in such a way that to discuss it competently, the students need some knowledge. For instance, in the freeway construction dilemma presented above, the students ask questions about the economic advantage of having freeways, whether freeways lead to more traffic, how much soil is needed for a freeway, what the consequences of the sealing of the soil are, which harmful substances are emitted by cars and how harmful they are, whether fast driving pollutes more than slow driving, etc. They soon recognize that they need information, and ask questions about facts (*Is*). The students are then asked to search for answers to these questions themselves, using any available source like the internet, books, etc.; they can also ask the teacher, who might be competent in the domain of knowledge. The procedure involves a typical constructivist approach (see DT' 1.2 in fig. 2) and follows the principles of inquiry-based learning (e.g., Dobber et al., 2017; Furtak et al., 2012; Pedaste et al., 2015).

After the search phase and the exchanging of information, the students engage in a new discussion on the values preferences, this time on a higher level since they now can capitalize on the newly acquired knowledge. They proceed in a similar way as do the practitioners of figure 3, although in contrast to those, they have time to discuss and to come to a collaborative decision, and they decide not for themselves but for a fictional protagonist so that they can disregard personal values

if they so want. In particular, in these discussions they combine values arguments (*Ought*) with facts they have identified in their search (*Is*), thus performing a TDA as action on the superordinate level (fig. 2). Experience shows that the students always combine several knowledge domains and refer to different ethical theories; this means that their discussions are also based on TDA's¹ on the subordinate level (fig. 2), with the content domains (GT' 1) adapted to the topic, as in figure 4. According to the principles of super- and subordinate TDAs, each of the domain-specific theories DT 1, DT 2, etc., can be a TDA' of its own—in the ecological issues, for instance, one can distinguish the domains of pollution, soil sealing, noise, etc., and within pollution a TDA' with CO₂, nitric oxides, hydrogen sulfides, etc. And the same principle can be applied to the *Ought* domain.

Figure 4: Possible TDA' for the DT 1 (*Is*) for the freeway dilemma

One can also conceive of a TDA where *Is* and *Ought* are related to each other on a subordinate level, as shown in figure 5 for the topic of the nitric oxides that are emitted by cars. These have an impact on human health, on acid rain, on ozone, etc., which in turn have specific consequences (for simplification, the impact and its consequences are combined on the subordinate level in fig. 5). These impacts and consequences are scientific facts, hence belonging to the *Is* domain. With respect to the *Ought* domain, the values of the respective issues (e.g., health and its consequences) are addressed. There is therefore a link between the *Is* issues and the corresponding *Ought* issues as they address the same topic, respectively, but once from the descriptive (DT' 1.1, etc.) and once from the normative (DT' 2.1, etc.) perspective.

It is important to emphasize that in VaKE, the respective TDAs are achieved not (only) by the individual students, but as a collaborative endeavor and achievement, with all students contributing their respective perspectives, values priorities and justifications, and knowledge base to the final decision about what the protagonist in the dilemma should do; this decision, then, is supported by arguments relating to *Is* as well as to *Ought*. Such a collaborative work requires communication, i.e., the students need to make their knowledge base and their values and justifications explicit and expose them to a check whether they are considered valid by the peers; the latter, in turn, have to make explicit why they do or do not accept the respective arguments. This satisfies the requirement of transparency that has been expressed above as a condition for scientific work—

¹ The prime symbol does not always refer to the same super- and sub-ordinate level; rather, it represents the super- and subordinate structure in the direct context, hence the same level is sometimes called TDA when superordinate and TDA' when subordinate.

tacit insinuations of values are not eliminated, but reduced to a minimum. In particular, the values on which the participants spontaneously agree are not discussed as they are not contested. These collectively accepted values can, to some degree, have the function of “highest value” in the third possibility of the Münchhausen trilemma discussed above.

Super-ordinate level	General Theory (GT) Theory about nitric oxides							
	Domain-Specific Theory DT 1 <i>Is</i>				Domain-Specific Theory DT 2 <i>Ought</i>			
Sub-ordinate level	GT' 1 = DT 1 <i>Impacts and consequences</i>				GT' 2 = DT 2 <i>Related values</i>			
	DT' 1.1 Impact on health and consequences	DT' 1.2 Impact on acid rain and consequences	DT' 1.3 Impact on ozone and consequences	DT' 1.3 ...	DT' 2.1 Value of health and consequences	DT' 2.2 Value of acid rain and consequences	DT' 2.3 Value of ozone and consequences	DT' 2.4 ...

Figure 5: Addressing the same issues from the *Is* and from the *Ought* perspective

In consequence, the students learn three competences:

- Within the *Is* domain, they learn many walk competences (in the sense of the competence to do something): to ask questions about necessary knowledge in specific situation; to search for responses to their questions; to judge which information (and information sources) are trustworthy and which ones are not (“fake news”); to put information from different domains in relation to each other (TDA' with respect to the *Is* domain); to apply information in a given concrete situation; and to use information on a higher level according to the Bloom et al. (1956) taxonomy (analysis, synthesis, evaluation)—in contrast to traditional teaching which, it seems, focuses on the lower taxonomical levels (knowledge, understanding, application); etc. And they learn talk competence by acquiring knowledge.
- As to the *Ought* domain, they learn a series of walk competences: to recognize that most situations with which they are confronted in their everyday life involve values (moral sensitivity); to make the values involved in such situations explicit; to consider different values and different types of values simultaneously (TDA' with respect to the *Ought* domain); to recognize the need to argue in favor of or against values; to see that other people may defend other values, and with good reasons, and to accept that they do so without taking over their position; to argue in favor of or against values on a higher competence level than heretofore; to put themselves in the shoes of others who defend different perspectives; etc. On the talk level, they learn to esteem general values like human dignity, care for the environment, etc.
- With respect to walking the relationship between *Is* and *Ought*, finally, the students learn that the different issues or topics addressed in their discussion can be seen—and need to be seen—from both the *Is* and the *Ought* perspectives; to separate the

two perspectives, but to relate them to each other; to understand that the two perspective require different types of argumentation and criticism; etc.

All these learning effects have either been shown in systematic empirical studies (for an overview, see Weyringer et al., 2022), or at least there is anecdotal evidence for them. They involve both talk and walk competences. The talk competences refer to knowledge, sensitivity for values issues, and acknowledgment of the need to use both *Is* and *Ought* but to distinguish the different types of argumentation. The walk part that the participants learn refers to all the activities mentioned above.

Conclusion

The *Is-Ought* problem is a crucial topic in educational research as well as in educational practice. To be able to deal competently with it is further an important goal of education because it is a pre-requirement for solving crucial challenges to mankind. However, the problem has mainly been discussed on the levels of philosophy (meta-ethics, to some degree also ethics) and of practitioners' concepts (e.g., teachers' goals and the means they have to achieve them), which can be considered as *talk*, whereas little has been said about how actors actually handle this problem in practice and how this can be improved through education (*walk*). Because *Is* and *Ought* are addressed in different disciplines, the concept of transdisciplinarity can be used for the discussion of these issues; however, since disciplines are a sociological category and not an epistemological one, as would be necessary for the discussion of the *Is-Ought* problem, it seems appropriate to replace transdisciplinarity with another basic framework which we have called the Trans-Domain Approach (TDA). Doing this permits us to avoid the restrictions and disadvantages met when discussing the disciplines but still to capitalize on insight gained in discussions of transdisciplinarity. In particular, the distinction between TDA as a system of sentences (theories) and TDA as actions is relevant, and within the former, provides more detailed concepts of theory systems—both can be found in the literature on transdisciplinarity and have proved fruitful in the concept of TDA.

The analyses presented above showed how useful the concept of TDA is. In particular, it was possible to deal with all the issues that were addressed without caring whether the frameworks at stake were from different disciplines or not. Admittedly, the concept of domains as used above is to some degree fuzzy, and the definition of a domain may vary from one analysis to another—for instance, what was treated as one domain on the superordinate level was divided into several sub-domains in the subordinate level—and there is not one and only one way to conceive domains and sub-domains for a given topic (research problem, dilemma, etc.). Rather, one can conceive of different TDA structures depending on the topic, the type of problem one addresses, and the way one attempts to solve it (this was also the reason why transdisciplinarity was required in the first place; OECD/CERI, 1972). But on the other hand, the topics we have to deal with in today's world are so complex that there is no one single way to deal with them; in fact, it is necessary to use different approaches simultaneously (Patry, 2013).

The analysis also showed that transdisciplinarity or Trans-Domain Approaches are not just academic constructions or research concepts. Rather, they have a direct impact on our lives. With respect to the *Is-Ought* problem, the concept of TDA with its treating *Is* and *Ought* as different domains permits, on the level of the talk (theory-building), to overcome the deadlock advanced in

Hume's (1739) thesis of the strict separation of *Is* and *Ought* with claims like the requirement that educational research must not make normative statements (Brezinka, 1994) or that science is values-free. Both claims cannot be satisfied, as research will always be values laden, especially educational research, since education aims at achieving goals which necessarily have a normative base. On the level of walk (acting or deciding to act based on more or less general principles), the TDA as action as proposed in figure 3 (theory-practice transfer) has proven to be fruitful. And finally, with respect to values and knowledge education for students, the TDA was fruitful in analyzing the students' discussions in *VaKE* as well as in accounting for their learning, with respect to both the talk and the walk.

On the other hand, *VaKE* was shown to be quite a useful teaching-learning tool in helping students talk and walk in the field of *Is* and *Ought*. In particular, our world and its challenges need people who recognize the urgency of intervening beyond one's immediate benefit but in the interest of humankind or even the planet, including its future, as can be seen with the climate crisis. This need requires that the people defend societal values (*Ought*). But such values are blind if not combined with knowledge about facts (*Is*) which permit the diagnostics and targeted interventions needed to overcome the challenges. In other words, the two domains must be combined on the different (superordinate and subordinate) levels. *VaKE* is an educational approach that does just this. The claim is not that it is the only approach to achieving that goal, but at least it is one possible way.

References

- Albert, H. (1985). M. V. Rorty (trans.). *Treatise on critical reason*. Princeton University Press.
- Arnold, M. L. (2000). Stage, sequence, and sequels: Changing conceptions of morality, post-Kohlberg. *Educational Psychology Review* 12 (4), pp. 365-383.
- Baggaley, R., Garcia Calleja, J. M., Marum, L., & Marum, E. (2013). Knowledge is power; information is liberation. *Bulletin of the World Health Organization* 91, p. 898. <https://doi.10.2471/BLT.13.132464>. Accessed 17 May 2025.
- Balsiger, P. W. (2005). *Transdisziplinarität: Systematisch-vergleichende Untersuchung disziplinenübergreifender Wissenschaftspraxis*. Fink.
- Bauer, M. A., & Meyerhuber, M. I. (eds.). (2020). *Empirical research and normative theory: Transdisciplinary perspectives on two methodical traditions between separation and interdependence*. De Gruyter Brill. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110613797-005>; <https://www.degruyter.com/document/doi/10.1515/9783110613797/html#contents>. Accessed 17 May 2025.
- Bloom, B. S., Engelhart, M. D., Furst, E. J., Hill, W. H., & Krathwohl, D. R. (eds.). (1956). *Taxonomy of educational objectives: The classification of educational goals. Handbook 1: Cognitive domain*. Longmans, Green & Co.
- Brezinka W. (1994). *Basic concepts of educational science: Analysis, critique, proposals*. University Press of America.
- Bromme, R., & Kienhues, D. (2014). Wissenschaftsverständnis und Wissenschaftskommunikation. In T. Seidel & A. Krapp (eds.). *Pädagogische Psychologie*, 6th ed. (pp. 55-81). Beltz.
- Burghardt, D., Krininger, D., & Seichter, S. (eds.). (2015). *Pädagogischer Takt: Theorie – Empirie – Kultur*. Schöningh.
- Burghardt, D., & Zirfas, J. (2019). *Der pädagogische Takt: Eine erziehungswissenschaftliche Problemformel*. Beltz.
- Curry, O. (2006). Who's afraid of the naturalistic fallacy? *Evolutionary Psychology* 4, pp. 234-247.
- Daston, L. (2014). The naturalistic fallacy is modern. *Isis: An International Review Devoted to the History of Science and its Cultural Influences* 105 (30), pp. 579-587. <https://pure.mpg>.

de/rest/items/item_2280702_10/component/file_3047843/content. Accessed 17 May 2025.

Dobber, M., Zwart, R., Tanis, M., & van Oers, B. (2017). Literature review: The role of the teacher in inquiry-based education. *Educational Research Review* 22, pp. 194-214.

Elliott, J. (1978). What is action-research in schools? *Journal of Curriculum Studies* 10 (4), pp. 355-357. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0022027780100407>. Accessed 17 May 2025.

---. (2015). Educational action research as the quest for virtue in teaching. *Educational Action Research* 23 (1), pp. 4-21.

Faust, D. (1984). *The limits of scientific reasoning*. University of Minnesota Press.

Friedrich, J. (2005). Naturalistic fallacy errors in lay interpretations of psychological science: Data and reflections on the Rind, Tromovitch, and Bauseman (1998) controversy. *Basic and Applied Social Psychology* 27 (1), pp. 59-70.

---. (2010). Naturalistic fallacy errors and behavioral science news: The effects of editorial content and cautions on readers' moral inferences and perceptions of contributors. *Basic and Applied Social Psychology* 32, pp. 369-383.

Furtak, E. M., Seidel, T., Iverson, H., & Briggs, D. C. (2012). Experimental and quasi-experimental studies of inquiry-based science teaching: A meta-analysis. *Review of Educational Research* 82, pp. 300-329.

Gardner, H. (1993). *Multiple intelligences: The theory in practice*. HarperCollins.

Gastager, A., & Patry, J.-L. (eds.). (2018). *Pädagogischer Takt: Analysen zu Theorie und Praxis*. Leykam.

Groeben, N., Wahl, D., Schlee, J., & Scheele, B. (eds.). (1988). *Forschungsprogramm subjektive Theorien: Eine Einführung in die Psychologie des reflexiven Subjekts*. Francke. <http://www.ssoar.info/ssoar/handle/document/2765>. Accessed 17 May 2025.

Hamlin, J. K., & Tan, E. (2020). The emergence of moral responses and sensitivity. In L. A. Jensen (ed.). *The Oxford handbook of moral development: An interdisciplinary perspective* (pp. 267-287). Oxford University Press. <https://www.oxfordhandbooks.com/view/10.1093/oxfordhb/9780190676049.001.0001/oxfordhb-9780190676049-e-15?print=pdf> Accessed 17 May 2025.

Herbart, J. F. (1802/1896). *Herbart's ABC of sense-perception and minor pedagogical works, translated, with introduction, notes, and commentary, by William J. Eckoff, 1896*. Appleton. http://www.archive.org/stream/herbartsbcofsens00herbuoft/herbartsbcofsens00herbuoft_djvu.txt. Accessed 17 May 2025.

- Herrmann, T. (1979a). *Psychologie als Problem: Herausforderungen der psychologischen Wissenschaft*. Klett.
- . (1979b). Pädagogische Psychologie als psychologische Technologie. In J. Brandtstädter, G. Reinert & K. A. Schneewind (eds.). *Pädagogische Psychologie: Probleme und Perspektiven* (pp. 209-236). Kohlhammer.
- Hume, D. (1739). *A treatise of human nature. Reprinted from the original edition in three volumes and edited, with an analytical index, by L. A. Selby-Bigge*. Clarendon Press, 1896. <https://people.rit.edu/wlrgsh/HumeTreatise.pdf>. Accessed 17 May 2025.
- Jantsch, E. (1947). Inter-and transdisciplinary university: A systems approach to education and innovation. *Higher Education Quarterly* 1 (4), pp. 403-428. <https://www.jstor.org/stable/4531408>. Accessed 17 May 2025.
- Judge, A. (1991). Metaphors as transdisciplinary vehicles of the future: Science and tradition. In Union des Ingénieurs et des Techniciens utilisant la Langue Française (eds.). *Congrès science et tradition: Perspectives transdisciplinaires, ouvertures vers le XXIème siècle*. <https://www.laetusinpraesens.org/docs/transveh.php>. Accessed 17 May 2025.
- Kant, I. (1956). *Kritik der reinen Vernunft: Unveränderter Neudruck der von Raymund Schmidt besorgten Ausgabe (nach der zweiten durchgesehenen Auflage von 1930)*. Meiner. <https://vdoc.pub/documents/kritik-der-reinen-vernunft-2s13pa6mfo0g>. Accessed 17 May 2025.
- Kincaid, H., Dupré, J., & Wylie, A. (eds.). (2007). *Value-free science? Ideals and illusions*. Oxford University Press.
- Klafki, W. (1984). Der Begriff der Didaktik und der Satz vom Primat der Didaktik (im engeren Sinne) im Verhältnis zur Methodik. In W. Klafki, G. M. Rückheim, W. Wolf, R. Freudenstein, H.-K. Beckmann, K.-C. Lingelbach, G. Iben & J. Diederich (eds.), *Funkkolleg Erziehungswissenschaft* (Bd. 2) (pp. 55-73). Fischer.
- Kohlberg, L. (1971). From is to ought: How to commit the naturalistic fallacy and get away with it in the study of moral development. In T. Mischel (ed.) *Cognitive development and epistemology* (pp.151-235). Academic Press.
- . (1981). *The philosophy of moral development: Moral stages and the idea of justice*. Essays on moral development Vol. 1: Harper & Row.
- . (1984). *The psychology of moral development: The nature and validity of moral stages*. Essays on moral development Vol. 2. Harper & Row.
- Lapsley, D. & Narvaez, D. (2005). Moral psychology at the crossroads. In D. Lapsley & C. Power (eds). *Character psychology and character education* (pp. 18-35). University of Notre Dame Press.

- Lind, G. (2016). *How to teach morality: Promoting deliberation and discussion, reducing violence and deceit*. Logos.
- Mahoney, M. J. (1976). *Scientist as subject: The psychological imperative*. Ballinger.
- Mischel, W., & Shoda, Y. (1995). A cognitive-affective system theory of personality: Reconceptualizing situations, dispositions, dynamics, and invariance in personality structure. *Psychological Review* 102, pp. 246-268.
- Mittelstrass, J. (2018). The order of knowledge: From disciplinarity to transdisciplinarity and back. *European Review* 26 (Suppl S2), pp. S68-S75. https://www.cambridge.org/core/services/aop-cambridgecore/content/view/8ED86874D100DA377C7151A8BCEB73E0/S1062798718000273a.pdf/order_of_knowledge_from_disciplinarity_to_transdisciplinarity_and_back.pdf. Accessed 18 May 2025.
- Morscher, E. (2018). Metaethics and moral education. In A. Weinberger, H. Biedermann, J.-L. Patry & S. Weyringer (eds.). *Professionals' ethos and education for responsibility* (pp. 17-27). Brill.
- . (2021). *Vom metaethischen Non-Kognitivismus zur Indeterminiertheit der Normativen Ethik*. Academia.
- Newberry, K. M., Feller, D. P., & Bailey, H. R. (2021). Influences of domain knowledge on segmentation and memory. *Memory & Cognition* 49 (4), pp. 660-674.
- Nussbaumer, M. (2009). *“Argumentieren geht über Studieren”*: Wie Schülerinnen und Schüler im didaktischen Konzept VaKE argumentieren. Unpublished master's thesis, Paris-Lodron University Salzburg.
- Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, Centre for Educational Research and Innovation (OECD/CERI) (ed.). (1972). *Interdisciplinarity: Problems of teaching and research in universities*. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED061895.pdf>. Accessed 18 May 2025.
- Patry, J.-L. (1989). Warum hat die Erziehungswissenschaft so wenig Einfluss auf die Erziehung? *Die Realschule* 97, pp. 107-113.
- . (1991a). Der Geltungsbereich sozialwissenschaftlicher Aussagen: Das Problem der Situationsspezifität. *Zeitschrift für Sozialpsychologie* 22, pp. 223-244.
- . (1991b). *Transsituationale Konsistenz des Verhaltens und Handelns in der Erziehung*. Peter Lang.

- . (2005). Intrapersonaler Wertpluralismus in der Erziehung: Theorie und konkrete Beispiele. In C. Giordano & J.-L. Patry (eds.). *Wertkonflikt und Wertewandel. Eine pluridisziplinäre Begegnung* (pp. 135-150). Lit.
- . (2006). Die Werturteilsproblematik in der Erziehungswissenschaft. In G. Zecha (ed.). *Werte in den Wissenschaften* (pp. 279-302). Mohr Siebeck.
- . (2011). Methodological consequences of situation specificity: biases in assessments. *Frontiers in Psychology* 2. http://www.frontiersin.org/quantitative_psychology_and_measurement/10.3389/fpsyg.2011.00018/abstract. Accessed 18 May 2025.
- . (2012). Antinomien in der Erziehung. In C. Nerowski, T. Hascher, M. Lunkenbein & D. Sauer (eds.). *Professionalität im Umgang mit Spannungsfeldern der Pädagogik* (pp. 177-187). Klinkhardt.
- . (2013). Beyond multiple methods: Critical multiplism on all levels. *International Journal of Multiple Research Approaches* 7, pp. 50-65. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.5172/mra.2013.7.1.50>. Accessed 18 May 2025.
- . (2014). Rivalisierende Paradigmen in der Erziehungswissenschaft: Das Beispiel der Situationsspezifität. In S. Kornmesser & G. Schurz (eds.). *Die multiparadigmatische Struktur der Wissenschaften* (pp. 103-144). Springer VS.
- . (2016). Thesen zur konstruktivistischen Didaktik. *journal für lehrerInnenbildung* 16 (2), pp. 9-17.
- . (2017, August 29-September 2). *The generality-concreteness antinomy, variance accounted for, and situation specificity*. 17th Biennial EARLI Conference, within the Invited Symposium of SIG 25 “The Role of Theory in Empirical Research on Education.”
- . (2018). Theorie-Praxis-Transfer: Hindernisse und Probleme. In A. Gastager & J.-L. Patry (eds.). *Pädagogischer Takt: Analysen zu Theorie und Praxis* (pp. 17-42). Leykam.
- . (2019). Situation specificity of behavior: The triple relevance in research and practice of education. In R. V. Nata (ed.). *Progress in education* 58 (pp. 29-144). Nova.
- . (2022a). From trans-disciplinary research to Trans-Domain Approaches. *The Journal of Systemics, Cybernetics and Informatics* 20 (3), pp. 1-12. <http://www.iiisci.org/journal/sci/issue.asp?is=ISS2203>. Accessed 18 May 2025.
- . (2022b). Practicing transdisciplinarity in education: Values and Knowledge Education (VaKE). *Journal of Systemics, Cybernetics and Informatics* 20 (6), pp. 66-71. <https://doi.org/10.54808/JSCI.20.06.66>. Accessed 18 May 2025.
- Patry, J.-L., Diekmann, N., & Weyringer, S. (2022). Transdisciplinarity and trans-domain approaches in VaKE. In S. Weyringer, J.-L. Patry, D. Pnevmatikos & F. Brossard Børhaug

- (eds.). *The VaKE handbook: Theory and practice of Values and Knowledge Education* (pp. 370-388). Brill.
- Patry, J.-L., & Patry, P. (2003). Werte und Normen in den Sozialwissenschaften. In A. Hieke & O. Neumaier (eds.). *Philosophie im Geiste Bolzanos: anlässlich des 222. Geburtstages von Bernard Bolzano, Edgar Morscher gewidmet* (pp. 199-222). Academia.
- Patry, J.-L., Weinberger, A., & Weyringer, S. (in prep.). Combining Values and Knowledge Education (working title). To be published in B. J. Irby, R. Lara-Alecio, N. Abdelrahman & M. J. Etchells (eds.). *Handbook of educational theories* (working title).
- Patry, J.-L., & Weyringer, S. (2019). Transdisziplinarität bei der Unterrichtsmethode „Values and Knowledge Education“: Grundlagen und die Beziehung zwischen Sein und Sollen. *Itdb: Inter- und transdisziplinäre, Bildung* 1, pp. 45-56. <https://itdb.ch/index.php/itdb/article/view/1185/1095>. Accessed 18 May 2025.
- Pedaste, M., Maeots, M., Siiman, L. A., de Jong, T., van Riesen, S., Kamp, E., Manoli, C., Zacharia, Z., & Tsourlidaki, E. (2015). Phases of inquiry-based learning: Definitions and the inquiry cycle. *Educational Research Review* 14, pp. 47-61. doi: 10.1016/j.edurev.2015.02.003. Accessed 18 May 2025.
- Piaget, J. (1972). The epistemology of interdisciplinary relationships. In Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development, Centre for Educational Research and Innovation (OECD/CERI) (ed.). *Interdisciplinarity: Problems of teaching and research in universities* (pp. 127-139). <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/ED061895.pdf> Accessed 18 May 2025.
- . (1985). *The equilibration of cognitive structures: The central problem of intellectual development*. University of Chicago Press.
- Rest, J. R., Narvaez, D., Thoma, S. J., & Bebeau, M. J. (2000). A neo-kohlbergian approach to morality research. *Journal of Moral Education* 29 (4), pp. 381-395. <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/713679390>. Accessed 18 May 2025.
- Reynolds, S. J., & Miller, J. A. (2015). The recognition of moral issues: Moral awareness, moral sensitivity and moral attentiveness. *Current Opinion in Psychology* 6, pp. 114-117. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2352250X15001852?via%3Dihub>. Accessed 18 May 2025.
- Rogerson, M. D., Gottlieb, M. C., Handelsman, M. M., Knapp, S., & Younggreen, J. (2011). Nonrational processes in ethical decision making. *American Psychologist* 66 (7), pp. 614-623.
- Roither, I. (2014). *Die Bedeutung Subjektiver Theorien von Praxislehrpersonen in der Unterrichtsbesprechung: Eine explorative Studie im Setting der Schulpraktischen Ausbildung an Hauptschulen und Neuen Mittelschulen im Unterrichtsfach Englisch*. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, Paris-Lodron University Salzburg.

- Rosenfield, P. (1992). The potential of transdisciplinary research for sustaining and extending linkages between the health and social sciences. *Social Science & Medicine* 35, pp. 1343-1357.
- Rousseau, D., Wilby, J., Billingham, J., & Blachfellner, S. (2018). *General systemology: Transdisciplinarity for discovery, insight and innovation*. Springer Singapore. <https://link.springer.com/book/10.1007%2F978-981-10-0892-4>. Accessed 18 May 2025.
- Scholz, R. W., & Steiner, G. (2015). The real type and ideal type of transdisciplinary processes: Part I—theoretical foundations. *Sustainability Science* 10, pp. 527-544.
- Schurz, G. (1995). Grenzen rationaler Ethikbegründung: Das Sein-Sollen-Problem aus moderner Sicht. *Ethik und Sozialwissenschaften: Streitforum für Erwägungskultur* 6 (2), pp. 163-177.
- . (1997). *The is-ought problem: A study in philosophical logic*. Kluwer.
- . (2004). Zur Rolle von Brückenprinzipien in einer faktenorientierten Ethik. In C. Lütge & G. Vollmer (eds.). *Fakten statt Normen? Zur Rolle einzelwissenschaftlicher Argumente in einer naturalistischen Ethik* (pp. 14-27). Nomos.
- . (2010). Non-trivial versions of Hume's is-ought thesis and their presuppositions. In C. Pigden (ed.). *Hume on 'is', and 'ought'* (pp. 198-216). Palgrave Macmillan.
- . (2020). Vom Sein zum Sollen: Nichtreligiöse Moralbegründungen. *Theologie für die Praxis* 46, pp. 98-109.
- Shoda, Y., & Mischel, W. (2006). Applying meta-theory to achieve generalisability and precision in personality science. *Applied Psychology: An International Review* 55, pp. 439-452.
- Thoma, S. J. (2014). Measuring moral thinking from a neo-Kohlbergian perspective. *Theory and Research in Education* 12 (3), pp. 347-365. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/1477878514545208>. Accessed 18 May 2025.
- United Nations. (1948). *The universal declaration of human rights*. <https://www.ohchr.org/EN/UDHR/Pages/UDHRIndex.aspx>. Accessed June 23, 2020.
- Van Assche, K. (2013). Understanding the nature of disciplinary boundaries as a reason for success in interdisciplinary research. In B. Tress, G. Tress, A. Van der Valk & G. Fry (eds.). *Interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary landscape studies: Potential and limitations* (pp. 100-106). WUR, Alterra.
- von Glasersfeld, E. V. (1995). *Radical constructivism: A way of knowing and learning*. The Falmer Press.

- Weingart, P. (2000). Interdisciplinarity: The paradoxical discourse. In P. Weingart & N. Stehr (eds.). *Practising interdisciplinarity* (pp. 25-42). University of Toronto Press/De Gruyter. <https://doi.org/10.3138/9781442678729-004>. Accessed 18 May 2025.
- Weingart, P., & Stehr, N. (2000). Introduction. In P. Weingart & N. Stehr (eds.). *Practising interdisciplinarity* (pp. xi-xvi). University of Toronto Press.
- Weyringer, S., Patry, J.-L., Pnevmatikos, D., Brossard Børhaug, F. (eds.). (2022). *The VaKE handbook: Theory and practice of Values and Knowledge Education*. Brill.
- Williams, B. (1973). Ethical consistency. In B. Williams (ed.). *Problems of the self: Philosophical papers 1956-1972* (pp. 166-186). Cambridge University Press. doi:10.1017/CBO9780511621253.013. Accessed 18 May 2025.
- Zecha, G. (1984). *Für und wider die Wertfreiheit der Erziehungswissenschaft*. Fink/Schöningh.